

Artificial intelligence in wastewater treatment plants: a review of current trends and adaptation strategies in the face of climate-driven rainfall fluctuations

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ABSTRACT

Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) are encountering challenges related to sustainability, efficiency, and economic viability due to stricter discharge standards and the impact of climate change, including heavy rainfall. Enhancing the resilience and performance of WWTPs is therefore crucial. This paper reviews the application of artificial intelligence (AI) models that can improve WWTP resilience in response to extreme rainfall events. It provides an overview of publications on digitalization of WWTPs over the past 33 years, proposes a new classification approach for AI models, and reviews existing AI applications aimed at improving the performance of WWTPs in response to extreme rainfall events. These applications highlight the importance of developing hybrid models that integrate AI with knowledge-driven models to improve accuracy. Furthermore, future AI research in WWTPs should incorporate hydrological forecasting to enable advance estimation of flow rates, and facilitate effective management.

Key words: climate resilience, data mining, environmental sustainability, operational optimization, wastewater treatment

HIGHLIGHTS

- Comprehensive review of 33 years of WWTP digitalization trends.
- A new paradigm for the classification of AI models in WWTP is suggested.
- Key barriers limiting AI adoption in WWTP operations highlighted.
- Hybrid models integrating data and knowledge-driven approaches improve accuracy.
- Future AI research should integrate WWTP modeling with hydrological forecasting.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

1. INTRODUCTION

Wastewater treatment aims to remove pollutants to ensure that treated water meets environmental regulations for safe discharge into receiving water bodies (Al-Dahidi *et al.* 2024). Wastewater treatment is a complex process involving multiple stages, thereby presenting various challenges related to its operation and management. These include fluctuating influent flows, varying wastewater characteristics and environmental conditions, and also a range of administrative challenges, including supply-chain-related problems (Zhang *et al.* 2022; Li *et al.* 2023; Tse 2024).

The operation of WWTPs is currently challenged by the need to maintain sustainability, efficiency, and economic viability. This is largely due to stricter discharge standards for micropollutants and the growing concerns related to environmental issues, including the impacts of climate change (Bassin *et al.* 2021). In the case of the former, for example, new EU regulations mandate that all towns and cities with populations of 1,000 or more must implement secondary treatment for their wastewater before releasing it into the environment. Additionally, by 2039, municipalities with a population exceeding 150,000 are required to adopt tertiary treatment (Regulation 2024/2019). Moreover, the WWTPs have been recognized as one of the largest generators of minor greenhouse gases, contributing to climate change, while simultaneously being vulnerable to its effects (Kyung *et al.* 2015; Bassin *et al.* 2021). Climate change consequences, such as excessive rainfall, increased temperatures, salt intrusion, sea-level rise, and more frequent storms, can adversely affect WWTP operations and hinder their operational efficiency (Singh & Tiwari 2019; Ranieri *et al.* 2024). In the context of climate-induced rainfall fluctuations, which is the focus of the current study, the increasing occurrence of intense rainfall events has the potential to exceed the capacity of WWTPs due to increased flow rate and cause hydraulic overload and consequently deterioration of effluent quality, especially in urban areas with a combined sewer system that collects municipal wastewater alongside stormwater (Botturi *et al.* 2021). Additionally, these uncertainties create difficulties in achieving regulatory standards (Wang *et al.* 2021). Several studies have highlighted how climate-driven rainfall fluctuations can compromise WWTP performance by altering hydraulic loads, influent characteristics, and treatment efficiencies. For example, a study conducted by Aziz *et al.* (2024) examined the impact of severe wet weather on existing wastewater infrastructure, which is attributed to the combined effects of climate change. Their study highlighted the need for system upgrades and proposed the implementation of a digital twin for real-time monitoring and collection systems to effectively manage the increasing volumes of wastewater. Furthermore, Ranieri *et al.* (2024) conducted a regional study in Apulia (Southern Italy), revealing that increased rainfall intensity due to climate variability resulted in higher influent flow rates, ultimately increasing the specific energy consumption per unit of treated wastewater.

Smart cities should be designed to be resilient in the face of natural disasters and emergencies. In this regard, wastewater treatment systems are a critical component of disaster preparedness (Yogi & Chakravarthy 2024). Recently, advancements in digitalization have transformed the water sector from traditional decision-making to smart operational strategies that can revolutionize the way the world tackles climate change (Garrido-Baserba *et al.* 2020; Ratnaweera 2022; Kurniawan *et al.* 2024). Data-driven models enhance process visualization, accurate predictions, and effective system monitoring. The digital transformation, including big data, data analytics, as well as artificial intelligence (AI), digital tools such as sensors, digital twins, data mining, data pipelines, and internet of things (IoT), has significantly improved smart water management practices (Matheri *et al.* 2022).

In this context, AI offers significant potential to transform the planning and management of water infrastructure, thereby enhancing climate resilience in infrastructure systems (Argyroudis *et al.* 2022; Alprol *et al.* 2024). AI automates tasks normally performed by humans, including planning, searching, reasoning, and knowledge representation (Malviya & Jaspal 2021). It processes big data to simulate and predict complex, nonlinear, and large amounts of historical data series in a short time, using the ability of digital machines or software (Mustafa *et al.* 2021). Machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) are acknowledged as subfields within the larger domain of AI. ML focuses on analyzing input data to create algorithms for task automation, but often lacks clarity on data patterns and processing failures. DL enhances prediction and classification by understanding complex patterns (Nguyen *et al.* 2022). By continuously adapting to changing conditions, these algorithms improve their performance over time, transforming into robust threat detection systems that can contribute to the resilience and adaptability of wastewater treatment systems – ensuring that these systems remain effective under different circumstances (Yogi & Chakravarthy 2024). It is worth noting that each of these methods has its own advantages and limitations, which are discussed in more detail in sources such as Wang, Y. *et al.* (2023).

AI can be classified in various ways. Hassani *et al.* (2020) introduced a classification based on the evaluation of AI and AI-assisted machines in relation to the human brain, specifically their capacity to imitate human cognitive functions and emotions. On the other hand, the second categorization prioritizes the technological aspects (Figure 1). It is worth highlighting that genetic algorithms (GAs) stand out as optimization and search algorithms inspired by the process of biological evolution (Paszkowicz 2009). Therefore, they are not directly part of AI but rather can be used to optimize weights, network architecture, learning rules, neurons, activation functions, and biases (Abdolrasol *et al.* 2021).

Recently, several studies have focused on classifying AI techniques used in wastewater treatment (Zhao *et al.* 2020; Safeer *et al.* 2022; Wang, Y. *et al.* 2023). However, those classifications are inconsistent. For instance, data mining, suggested as an AI technique by Zhao *et al.* (2020), is not an AI technique but rather a domain in which AI can be applied. In other words, data mining refers to the use of computer-based techniques to derive insights from data (Kantardzic 2011). Additionally, the classification of optimization as one of the AI models for wastewater treatment by Wang, Y. *et al.* (2023) is inaccurate, as optimization is a method that can be integrated with other AI techniques (Xie *et al.* 2022).

This review provides an overview of the advancements in digitalization within the wastewater sector over the past 33 years and evaluates AI techniques used in WWTPs, highlighting their performance, strengths, and limitations, particularly in

Figure 1 | Artificial intelligence classification proposed by Hassani *et al.* (2020).

response to increased flow rates from heavy rainfall. Moreover, it proposes a new classification model for AI applications in WWTPs and addresses the challenges and requirements for further advancements in the field.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this review, a preliminary investigation was conducted on the Scopus database using digital keywords in conjunction with wastewater (Figure 2(a)) and PRISMA procedure (Moher *et al.* 2009). In the late 1980s and early 1990s, pioneering studies, such as Capodaglio *et al.* (1991) and Krovvidy *et al.* (1991), first published the application of AI for the operation and control of WWTPs. Accordingly, the literature search included studies from across the globe but was limited to the years 1990–2023. Studies not directly related to wastewater treatment and management were excluded from the review. The document type was restricted to ‘article’ and limited to English, resulting in 3,259 publications. The years were divided into two periods: 1990–2016, with 1,063 publications (32.62% of the total), and 2017–2023, with 2,196 publications (67.38% of the total). This reflects a significant increase in studies published in the last seven years, nearly doubling the output from 1990 to 2016. Annual publication trends are shown in Figure 2(b), highlighting a marked increase, especially after 2016.

It should be noted that the trend presented in Figure 2 is well aligned with long-term AI development periods, as illustrated in Figure 3 (adapted from Delipetrev *et al.* (2020)). In this figure, winters refer to the decline and springs to the growth of AI.

Figure 2 | (a) The keywords used in Elsevier’s Scopus database with queries TITLE-ABS-KEY and (b) number of publications from 1990 to 2023 which was obtained by literature search related to AI and ML in the wastewater sector.

Figure 3 | Illustrative visualization of AI periods.

encompasses a wide range of autonomous control techniques. The blue cluster focuses on remote sensing applications for water quality assessment, and the yellow and purple clusters address biological parameters and advanced treatment processes, respectively. From 2016 to 2023, four clusters with 842 items were identified. AI methods have significantly evolved from basic to comprehensive investigations, incorporating keywords and clusters like ML, DL, and remote sensing. Research has also shifted toward heavy metals, nanoparticles, dyes, and the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic that began in 2020.

A comparison of Figure 4(a) and 4(b) reveals several significant differences that highlight shifts in publication trends over time. The numerous lines in Figure 4(b) indicate a more integrated web of ideas, reflecting a rise in collaborative research, interdisciplinary studies, and new subfields. Since 2016, research on WWTP has focused on remote sensing, image processing, data handling, and automation.

3. AI MODELS IN THE WASTEWATER SECTOR

The last five years have seen an exponential increase in publications within the scientific community regarding the use of ML models in WWTPs (Duarte *et al.* 2024). Among these, artificial neural networks (ANNs) have the highest number of research articles, with over 700 published between 2013 and April 2022 (Safeer *et al.* 2022). One reason for this popularity could be that ANN outperforms other single models in terms of accuracy, with reported R -values ranging from 0.6289 to 0.998 and R^2 values from 0.616 to 0.997 (Ghaedi & Vafaei 2017; Najafzadeh & Zeinolabedini 2019). Furthermore, because of their effectiveness in managing complicated, multivariate, and nonlinear issues, ANNs are widely used. This ability is essential in wastewater treatment because several parameters, such as pH, biological oxygen demand (BOD), chemical oxygen demand (COD), and others, have complex and nonlinear connections with one another. Furthermore, ANNs' adaptability enables them to model a range of WWTP operations, including chemical, biological, and physical treatment techniques (Nagpal *et al.* 2024). Nonetheless, when wastewater treatment modeling involves incomplete data, fuzzy logic (FL) is the most often utilized technique since it uses linguistic expert rules to estimate missing data (Ansari *et al.* 2020).

It is important to note that numerous studies have found that hybrid models perform comparatively better than single models in terms of accuracy and precision (Asadi *et al.* 2020). Hybridization is the process of integrating two different models, either in parallel or in series, to produce a model that is more accurate than either of them. For example, hybrid models, such as neural fuzzy (NF) and adaptive neural fuzzy intelligent systems (ANFIS), combine the interpretability of FL with the learning capabilities of ANNs to provide more comprehensible models, aiding wastewater treatment operations (Mahshidnia & Jafarian 2016; Fu *et al.* 2018). In this regard, this study proposes a new paradigm for the classification of AI models employed in WWTPs, as presented in Table 1. The classification includes three main classes: Predictive, Detective, and AI-based Optimization. Predictive models can be divided into four categories: Prediction of system output, Prediction of system input, Prediction of byproducts, and Prediction of anomalies in the system. For example, the category of predictive

Table 1 | A new paradigm for the classification of AI models in WWTP

AI model class	Class categories	Application examples	Reference(s)
Predictive models	Prediction of output of the treatment system	Predicting effluent quality parameters and emissions of WWTP	Guo <i>et al.</i> (2015)
	Prediction of input into the system	Predicting energy consumption in WWTP Predicting inflow into the WWTP	Bagherzadeh <i>et al.</i> (2021) Wei <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	Prediction of byproducts	Predicting sludge amount Predicting biogas production	Bień & Bień (2023) Sun <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	Prediction of anomaly in the system	Predicting operational status of treatment units (e.g. membrane fouling, pump failure)	Kovacs <i>et al.</i> (2022) and Velimirović <i>et al.</i> (2021)
Detective models	Detection of fault in the system	Detecting sensor faults Detecting actuator faults	Mamandipoor <i>et al.</i> (2020) Zhou, J. <i>et al.</i> (2021)
	AI-based optimization models	Optimization of performance Optimization of costs Multiobjective optimization	Optimization of treatment processes (e.g. nitrogen removal process) Optimization of energy consumption Optimization of treatment cost and effluent quality

models deals with the prediction of various parameters of interest in WWTPs. This includes predicting effluent quality parameters and emissions from WWTPs, such as total dissolved solids (TDS), BOD₅, and COD in the effluent (e.g. study by Sharafati *et al.* (2020)). Detective models focus on detecting faults in wastewater systems. AI-based optimization models are categorized into Optimization of performance, Optimization of costs, and Optimization of multiobjectives. Although many articles exist for each of these groups, only a few articles are included in Table 1 as examples to keep it concise.

The application of AI in wastewater treatment involves three key steps: (1) problem identification, (2) data collection and preparation, and (3) selection and implementation of AI models. First, the specific problem is defined, followed by data collection from sources like online sensors and laboratory tests, depending on the objectives. The collected data is then prepared for use in AI models. Finally, the most suitable algorithm is selected to assist in resolving the identified issue (Nguyen *et al.* 2022). In this regard, the general workflow procedure for AI application in WWTPs is presented in Figure 5, specifically addressing problems, with a focus on issues related to heavy rainfall events induced by climate change.

4. APPLICATIONS OF AI MODELS IN IMPROVING WWTPS RESILIENCE UNDER EXTREME RAINFALL CONDITIONS

This section reviews and examines the application of AI to assist WWTPs in adapting to the challenges posed by climate change. It focuses on predictive, detective, and AI-based optimization models, which have the potential to contribute to the improved operation of WWTPs for the management of increased flow rates during heavy rainfall.

4.1. Predictive models

4.1.1. Prediction of influent flow and effluent quality parameters

Variations in influent flow rates and water quality challenge the operation and management of WWTPs, often due to seasonal changes and extreme weather events. Literature highlights the development of data-driven models to forecast inflows, addressing uncertainties linked to weather patterns. Key models include ANN (El-Din & Smith 2002), random forest (RF) (Zhou *et al.* 2019), and various ARIMA-type models (Jóhannesson *et al.* 2021), autoregressive moving average with exogenous inputs (ARMAX), nonlinear autoregressive (NARX), and long short-term memory networks (LSTM) (Giberti *et al.* 2024). These insights are crucial for understanding the variability in influent characteristics, operational conditions, and regulatory requirements that can impact wastewater treatment performance. By identifying and quantifying these

Figure 5 | General workflow procedure of AI application in WWTPs.

uncertainties using long- and short-term data analysis, existing studies demonstrate the capacity of these models to enable plant operators and managers to develop more robust strategies that can adapt to changing climate conditions and mitigate potential risks.

The differences in rain patterns and wastewater overflows significantly impact nutrient dynamics, leading to eutrophication, which poses a huge problem for receiving water bodies (Tian *et al.* 2024). The results of various studies have provided evidence that AI-based models are capable of predicting effluent water quality parameters with greater accuracy compared with mechanistic models (El-Rawy *et al.* 2021; Yang *et al.* 2022). Qiao *et al.* (2023) used the ANFIS methodology in MATLAB to assess the model's effectiveness in predicting pollutant removal in WWTPs. They forecasted output parameters – COD, suspended solids (SS), total phosphorus (TP), total nitrogen (TN), ammonium (NH₃-N), and pH. The study achieved satisfactory accuracy, with results within a 95% confidence interval and some R^2 values above 0.950. Another study that also used the ANFIS model was carried out by Awolusi *et al.* (2016). The study was applied at a full-scale sewage treatment plant, where the influent to the sewage treatment plant consists of 90% domestic sewage and 10% industrial sewage. The main objective of the work was to evaluate the operating conditions that influence the performance of the nitrification process using the ANFIS model. A study conducted by Zaghoul *et al.* (2020) compared the ANFIS and support vector regression (SVR) methods on a pilot scale in three sequential batch reactors (SBRs), using 440 samples collected from the three reactors: influent wastewater tank, mixed liquor in the reactors, and the effluent chamber. The parameters analyzed for influent and effluent samples were COD, NH₃-N, phosphates (PO₄), and pH. The parameters analyzed for all mixed liquor samples were: mixed liquor suspended solids (MLSS), mixed liquor volatile suspended solids (MLVSS), sludge volume index (SVI) at 5 min, SVI at 30 min, granule size, and temperature. The test results for the models showed reactor performance for unseen data with an average R^2 , nRMSE, sMAPE, and MASE of 91%, 0.21, 0.06, and 0.22%, respectively, for ANFIS, and 99%, 0.07, 0.006, and 0.01 for SVR, respectively. Accordingly, the SVR model performed better than the ANFIS model in terms of prediction errors and failures. Zaghoul & Achari (2022) simulated a full-scale biological nutrient removal process using ANN, ANFIS, and SVR models, with historical data collected from a wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) spanning 2010–2020. They analyzed 26 parameters collected at various reactor points. The ANN models achieved average R^2 , nRMSE, and sMAPE values of 63, 0.07, and 8.5%. The ANFIS models had averages of 45, 0.08, and 10.2%, while the SVR models recorded averages of 57, 0.07, and 9.4%. Fuck *et al.* (2024) used ML models to predict water quality parameters in two case studies: a simulated WWTP and a real industrial WWTP. Three ML algorithms – support vector machines (SVMs), multilayer perceptron (MLP), and RF – were applied. In the simulated case, parameters such as inlet flow (Q_{in} , m³/d) and TN in the effluent were analyzed, while the real case included Q_{in} (m³/d), COD_{in} (mg/L), and others. The MLP model performed best, achieving an R^2 of 0.72 for the simulated WWTP. However, due to data recording issues and the complexity of the real treatment system, the models did not perform well, limiting their effectiveness in decision-making. Manu & Thalla (2017) developed AI models for a full-scale biological WWTP to assess nitrogen removal efficiency in real-time. Data included 88 data points across seven variables: pH, total solids, COD, temperature, free ammonia, ammonia nitrogen (AN), and total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN). As a result of the research, it was found that the error associated with predicting TKN concentration in effluent, specifically the RMSE and the NSE, was significantly lower in both the training and testing stages of the SVM model, compared with the ANFIS model. The ANFIS model with Gbell MF seems to have the accepted accuracy in both the training and testing stages.

Some researchers have highlighted neural network-based models, such as feed-forward neural network (FFNN), in their application to WWTPs. Using the FFNN model, Mahmud & Wahab (2017) developed an aerobic granular sludge (AGS) model to predict COD effluents in WWTP. The methodology involved investigating the granulation process, stability, density, and performance of the granules at three different temperatures: 30, 40, and 50 °C. The input parameters were COD, total organic carbon (TOC), TP, TN, AN, MLSS, and output data for the model were COD. In the testing model at 30, 40, and 50 °C, the R^2 values were 91.17%, 91.14%, and 89.64%, respectively. Zaghoul *et al.* (2018) used FFNN to predict SBR performance in a pilot study with synthetic wastewater. The pilot reactors were seeded with return-activated sludge obtained from a WWTP. The model demonstrated $R^2 > 99\%$ and RMSE $< 5\%$. In another study (Li *et al.* 2023), data-driven DL methods were applied in order to model and predict the treatment of real municipal wastewater using anaerobic membrane bioreactors. The models used were an ML fully connected network, a convolutional neural network (CNN), and a densely connected convolutional network (DenseNet). Six parameters related to the experimental conditions (temperature of reactor, temperature of environment, temperature of influent, influent pH, influent COD, and flux) and eight parameters for wastewater treatment performance evaluation (effluent pH, effluent COD, COD removal efficiency, biogas composition

(CH₄, N₂, and CO₂), biogas production rate, and oxidation–reduction potential) were selected to establish the datasets. The DenseNet model showed a remarkable accuracy of 97.44%.

Overall, the aforementioned studies have demonstrated that the application of AI models in predicting influent and effluent parameters in WWTPs is both viable and highly effective. However, additional efforts are necessary to collect more comprehensive data and to establish a deeper understanding of the interrelationships among different parameters by employing more advanced algorithms.

4.1.2. Prediction of WWTP anomalies

Predicting anomalies in WWTPs is of great importance for maintaining the operational stability of treatment units and protecting the receiving environment. It not only helps ensure consistent effluent quality but also supports decision-making, which is particularly important for adapting WWTPs to climate-change-related challenges. Table 2 provides a summary of studies on the management challenges of pumping stations and WWTPs operating under increased overflow. It includes a classification of AI models, an evaluation of their performance, and a discussion of their limitations.

AI applications in anomaly prediction in WWTPs include the use of remote sensing technologies, IoT devices, and unmanned aerial vehicles (Andres *et al.* 2018; Sancho Martínez *et al.* 2020; Mohanty *et al.* 2024). A study by Moreno-Rodenas *et al.* (2021) presented the potential of camera-based AI solutions for the observation of fat, oil, and grease (FOG) in wastewater pumping stations. Uncontrolled FOG accumulation causes challenges in pumping systems, including equipment failure and overflow discharges, particularly during increased flow rates under heavy rain. In the study, optical imagery was processed through a deep learning computer vision that allows the describing of the accumulation rate and changes in shape. Furthermore, various information related to the pumping tank (water level, circularity, etc.) was collected. A CNN routine was developed to discriminate types of surfaces in images. Consequently, the findings demonstrated that camera-based observation of FOG dynamics in wastewater pumping stations could facilitate the identification of layers and inform pump cleaning operations. One of the major limitations of the applied solution was the inability to account for the vertical growth of FOG.

Monitoring activated sludge features is another crucial step for assessing the operational status of biological treatment systems, as it impacts sedimentation efficiency and effluent quality, especially during heavy rainfall. An emerging approach involves using image classification models to predict operational status and detect anomalies by identifying and classifying the morphological characteristics of sludge flocs. This method employs segmentation algorithms on image data to assess biological reaction efficiency and its effect on subsequent settling units, achieving approximately 95% classification accuracy (Khan *et al.* 2018; Satoh *et al.* 2021). Additionally, the SVI is also monitored as a key parameter. In a study by Bagheri *et al.* (2015), hybrid models combining ANNs and GAs were evaluated for predicting SVI. Both MLPANN-GA (multilayer perceptron) and RBFANN-GA (radial basis function) models achieved a mean average error below 3% of the input SVI values. However, the MLPANN-GA model demonstrated superior predictive and generalization capabilities compared with the RBFANN-GA model when handling experimental, testing, and prediction datasets.

Han *et al.* (2018) tested an intelligent detection method using the self-organizing recurrent radial basis function neural network (SORRBFNN) model to identify failure areas and the variables associated with sludge bulking. The proposed method was evaluated in both nonfault and fault scenarios. Overall findings revealed that predicting accuracy is reliable and precise within the nonfault case of WWTP, while predicting accuracy declined in the fault cases of WWTP. However, the detection accuracies achieved are satisfactory for the effective operation of WWTPs. Szeląg *et al.* (2020) compared a number of ANNs, including SVM, RF, boosted trees (BT), and logical regression (LR) for simulating the activated sludge bulking (or absence of bulking). RF and BT methods acquired a high degree of fit for the sludge bulking identification, and the results of the activated sludge simulation calculations were improved by 10% by including the values of wastewater quality indicators.

4.2. AI-based optimization models

The rise in rainfall leads to higher wastewater volumes, raising energy costs at WWTPs, as appropriate treatment and safe discharge require substantial energy (Hernández-Chover *et al.* 2018; Li *et al.* 2023). Therefore, forecasting energy consumption is crucial for power management and better decision-making in WWTPs (Ahmad & Chen 2018). Energy consumption varies based on treatment level, technology, plant capacity, and pollution load, ranging from 0.33 to 0.60 kWh/m³, making WWTPs major energy consumers, accounting for about 4% of US electrical energy use (Gude 2015). In a recent study, Ranieri *et al.* (2024) investigated the impact of climate change on the incoming flow of WWTPs from 2016 to 2020. The findings indicated that the rise in rainfall intensity (from 0.8 to 2.9 mm/min) was accompanied by a notable increase in electrical

Table 2 | Predictive model evaluations for WWTP anomalies

Type of AI model	Input parameters	Output parameters	Dataset	Performance	Drawback	Reference
CNN	Pump sump images	FOG layer dynamics (e.g. accumulation rate and changes in shape) and various hydraulic processes and parameters in the pump sump (e.g. the water level, surface flow velocity fields, vorticity, or circulation)	A total of 89 mosaicked images	0.978 accuracy during validation	Small training dataset and the inability to capture vertical growth of FOG layers	Moreno-Rodenas <i>et al.</i> (2021)
CNN	Active sludge floc images	Active sludge flocs and presence or absence of filamentous bacteria	154 images for 7 min. Over 12,000 images	Distinguished aggregated flocs from dispersed ones with high training accuracy (approximately 95%) and could recognize 10% morphological changes in the aggregated flocs to dispersed ones	Concerns about the different operational conditions	Satoh <i>et al.</i> (2021)
SVM	Active sludge floc images	Morphology of flocs	130 samples from 9 different WWTPs, more than 11,014 images	Classification accuracy of 94.23% for the test data	Data imbalance, and the complexity of biological systems	Khan <i>et al.</i> (2018)
MLPANN-GA and RBFANN-GA	MLVSS, pH, DO, temperature, TSS, COD, and TN	SVI	750 days (76 total data points)	The GA increased the accuracy of all the MLPANN and RBFANN models	The complexity of biological systems, data dependency, limited scope of input variables	Bagheri <i>et al.</i> (2015)
SORRBFNN	MLSS, DO concentration, temperature T, BOD, COD, and TN	SVI	A set of 600 data as the training samples and 450 data for training	The detection accuracy of fault variables is 100% and the detection accuracies of fault points are 94% for DO and 87% for COD in the single-variable fault case	Reliance on specific datasets limit its generalizability	Han <i>et al.</i> (2018)
BT, RF, MLP, SVM, LR	BOD, COD, TSS, TN, TP, N-NH ₄ , and sedimentation parameters of activated sludge	SVI	The data were recorded at hourly intervals using SCADA 250 datasets	Soft sensors require more independent variables for reliable results	Model predictive power varies with variable combinations, highlighting the need for systematic feature selection to ensure robustness across conditions	Szeląg <i>et al.</i> (2020)

Table 3 | AI-based optimization models for energy consumption in WWTPs

Operational parameter	Type of AI model	Input parameters	Output parameters	Dataset	Performance	Reference
Aeration	RF, ADB, GB, XGB	BOD ₅	DO-energy demand	Three years and 2 months of operation, containing 1,155 daily readings: 808, 116, and 231 training, validation, and testing	An average of 23% energy and cost savings	Qambar & Al Khalidy (2022)
	VSL-ML	Temperature, wastewater flow rate, COD, NH ₄ ⁺ -N, TN	DO-energy demand	14,688 data from 153 days: a training set encompassing 14,208 samples (148 days) and a test set consisting of 480 samples (5 days)	16.12% reduction in demand compared with conventional aeration control of preset DO and feedback to the blower	Wang, Y. Q. et al. (2023)
	XGB-Bi-LSTM	COD, NH ₄ ⁺ -N, TP, and pH	Oxygen transfer efficiency and oxygen uptake rate	1,462 hourly readings from online sensors: 80% allocation designated for the purposes of training and validation, and a remaining 20% allotment set aside for subsequent testing	Energy consumption can be reduced by 23%	Ao et al. (2023)
Pumping stations	FL	Energy consumption of significant devices and operational conditions relating to wastewater inflow, pollution load, and wastewater composition	Daily energy decision-making for pump performance	90 days	Reducing 18.5% pump energy consumption	Torregrossa et al. (2017)
	Reinforcement learning	Historical sensor data	Pump electrical energy consumption	90 days	16.7% reduction in energy consumption	Filipe et al. (2019)
	Deep reinforcement learning	Historical data period from November 2018 to November 2019	Wastewater inflow forecasts, and electricity price related to pump usage	270 days	Reduction in energy consumption and costs of up to 4.18% and 4.66%, respectively	Seo et al. (2021)

consumption (from 0.36 to 0.51 kW/m³), demonstrating the importance of optimization of energy use in WWTPs to limit the global effects of climate change. WWTPs primarily consume energy for the aeration of activated sludge, which represents 45%–75% of their overall energy use. Significant contributors to energy consumption in wastewater treatment also include pumping, aerobic sludge stabilization, and dewatering, which make up 14.3%, 14.2%, and 3.9% of total electricity usage, respectively (Awe *et al.* 2016). Furthermore, Abunama *et al.* (2024) conducted a review of literature from 2013 to 2023 regarding ML techniques for energy optimization in WWTPs, highlighting their application in areas such as aeration, pumping, sludge treatment, and greenhouse gas emissions. The optimization models presented in Table 3 include case studies or examples that demonstrate successful implementations in various WWTPs, providing insights into the methodologies employed and the outcomes achieved.

4.2.1. Optimization of energy consumption in the aeration process

Many WWTPs use control systems that maintain a constant dissolved oxygen (DO) concentration of 2.0 mg/L. However, these systems often fail to account for fluctuating influent loadings, leading to inefficiencies and higher costs (Qambar & Al Khalidy 2022). Intense rainfall is a contributing factor to disturbances, necessitating more autonomous operation of nitrification and denitrification stages based on DO concentration (Hernández-del-Olmo *et al.* 2019). In the initial periods of studies, fuzzy neural networks (FNNs) were generally designed to provide aeration control for the purpose of energy and cost management in biological processes (Traore *et al.* 2005; Mingzhi *et al.* 2009). Additionally, the use of neural networks (NNs) was investigated by Lin & Luo (2016) to solve the DO concentration control problem using a disturbance observer. The combination of RBF neural networks and a nonlinear disturbance observer improves the system's robustness and disturbance attenuation capabilities.

In a recent study, Qambar & Al Khalidy (2022) employed ML methods, RF, adaptive boosting (ADB), gradient boosting (GB), and XGB algorithms to estimate DO concentration from the BOD₅ prediction model. All algorithmic models effectively predicted optimal DO requirements, with RF and GB achieving the best results: a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 1.00 and a mean absolute error (MAE) of 0.01, respectively. The analysis indicated that it is possible to achieve an average energy and cost saving of 23%. In another study, conducted by Ao *et al.* (2023), the aeration optimization approach based on the extreme gradient boosting–bidirectional long short-term memory (XGB-Bi-LSTM) model was applied for the online monitoring of oxygen transfer efficiency and oxygen uptake rate. The proposed optimization model diminished energy and cost consumption by 23%. The results were compatible with the findings of Qambar & Al Khalidy (2022), with an average of 23% energy and cost savings, achieved with RF and GB algorithms.

On the other hand, Wang, Y. Q. *et al.* (2023) presented an automatic feature ML model based on the variation sliding layer (VSL) to control and predict the air demand within the biochemical treatment process of WWTPs. The results indicated that the air demand was reduced by 16.12% in comparison with the standard aeration control method, which involves setting DO levels and giving feedback to the blower. The study suggests that additional validation of VSL and the creation of hybrid algorithms incorporating a variety of ML models are necessary to enhance accuracy and optimize model efficiency. These advancements could play a crucial role in maintaining treatment efficiency during periods of increased inflow due to heavy rainfall events.

4.2.2. Optimization of energy consumption of pumping stations

The impact of climate change on water levels is a significant factor during both dry and wet seasons. This has an additional strain on pumping stations, affecting their original flow capacity and hydraulic efficiency (Tse 2024). In the literature reviewed on the optimization of energy consumption based on AI models, many authors concentrated their attention very much on the pumping stations (e.g. Zhang *et al.* 2016; Seo *et al.* 2021). This specific attention arises from the fact that increasing water flow volumes necessitate enhanced capabilities for managing peak flows during storm events. Moreover, the occurrence of overflow conditions presents a considerable risk to the electrical, instrumentation, control, and automation systems in pumping systems (Tse 2024). To address this issue, several strategies can be implemented to prevent or decrease the effects of overflow.

Online sensors and advanced algorithms, as demonstrated by Torregrossa *et al.* (2017), can enable early detection of potential overflow scenarios. In their study, they utilized online sensors and FL algorithms to identify and analyze long-term and short-term trends in wastewater pumping systems. This approach resulted in the creation of a performance index that is easy for users to understand. By utilizing online sensors and employing FL algorithms, potential failures can be detected at an early

stage, and valuable information can be extracted from the database. To demonstrate the effectiveness of this approach, a case study was conducted on a WWTP in Germany. The findings revealed an 18.5% reduction in pump energy consumption by identifying energy inefficiencies and proposing solutions.

An alternative approach is to use advanced control systems that adjust pump speeds and schedules based on real-time data and forecasted inflow rates. *Filipe et al. (2019)* explored AI control using a reinforcement learning algorithm to optimize the operation of wastewater pumps. This paper presents a novel control strategy for variable-frequency pumps used in wastewater systems to minimize the electricity consumption by taking into account uncertainty forecasts for the wastewater intake rate and alarms (for tank level above limit) via information gathered from sensors. Therefore, the proposed method achieved a 16.7% reduction in energy consumption with respect to the current operating method and a 97% reduction in the number of alarms (wastewater level above maximum value). In addition, *Seo et al. (2021)* proposed a deep reinforcement learning pump control scheme designed for pumping systems that are operated in turning on/off signals to schedule the operation of the pumps. The study provided the mitigation of uncertainties caused by forecasting errors in view of energy consumption and cost, showing that their system performed as well as or better than experts at WWTPs in terms of operational rules.

5. CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

As demonstrated in the preceding sections, AI plays a critical role in advancing the management and control of WWTPs in the context of climate change. Specifically, AI enhances the capacity for weather-informed wastewater treatment by enabling predictive weather modeling and dynamic process optimization. This forecasting capability allows WWTPs to proactively respond to risks associated with extreme weather events, such as increased hydraulic loading. Moreover, AI-based control systems support operational resilience by autonomously adjusting key process parameters – such as aeration intensity and chemical dosing – in response to real-time weather data and forecast inputs (*Mohanty et al. 2024*). This adaptive functionality contributes to maintaining consistent treatment efficiency under variable and challenging climatic conditions. Despite the numerous successful applications of AI and ML in the field of wastewater treatment, several challenges may restrict the practical implementation of these sophisticated techniques on a wider scale. The general challenges associated with the application of AI and ML in WWTPs, and their utilization in enhancing resilience during periods of heavy rainfall, are (1) big data requirement, (2) reproducibility and transparency, (3) the need to improve AI knowledge and infrastructures in WWTPs, (4) integration of hydrological forecasts and WWTP operational models.

A major issue is the need for large datasets, which are often unavailable due to operational difficulties, sensor limitations, and high data collection costs, compounded by restrictive government data management practices (*Imen et al. 2023*). One way to address this challenge is data augmentation. This method expands the training data by enhancing it (*Demir et al. 2021*). Data augmentation techniques, such as simulating weather conditions, can help enhance training datasets. For challenging reproducibility and transparency of AI models, initiatives like Open Science and FAIR data principles aim to improve accessibility (*Quay et al. 2021*), and explainable AI (XAI) can clarify algorithmic processes (*Došilović et al. 2018; Rai 2020*). Another solution for transparency is hybrid modeling, which integrates data-driven and knowledge-driven models, creating hybrid models (*Zhou, T. et al. 2021*). These models are effective for studying the mechanisms of WWTP systems (*Wang, Y. et al. 2023*) and can save time by reducing the need for model calibration (*Hvala & Kocijan 2020*). Furthermore, water engineering has seen a growing interest in data-driven research (*Makropoulos & Savić 2019*). However, many plant managers lack data analysis skills, and the complexity of data management is worsened by a shortage of data science expertise. Training programs and integrating data science into water engineering education are essential (*Lowe et al. 2022; Bahramian et al. 2023*).

Finally, integrating hydrological forecasts with operational models is vital for resilience during heavy rainfall. This integration allows WWTPs to be prepared for potential challenges in advance, thereby reducing the risk of system overflows or failures (*El-Din & Smith 2002; Zhou et al. 2019; Fatone et al. 2021*). To achieve this, it is essential to engage in interdisciplinary collaboration between environmental engineering, data scientists, meteorology, hydrology, and civil engineering. A multidisciplinary approach enables a comprehensive examination of treatment facilities and their drainage basins, and it is thus possible to significantly enhance the preparedness and adaptability of wastewater systems during extreme weather events.

6. CONCLUSION

Climate change is one of the most serious environmental problems globally. WWTPs are among the facilities that will be seriously affected by the impacts of climate change, particularly extreme rainfall events. Digital technologies and AI

models are valuable tools for enhancing the resiliency of treatment plants through improved prediction, process optimization, and fault detection. This paper focused on AI models that can aid in managing increased flow rates during heavy rainfall events, driven by climate change, to prevent untreated wastewater discharges and ensure efficient system performance. The review includes progress in the area in the last 33 years, examples to the applications, and finally discusses the challenges. The main conclusions are as follows:

- ANFIS is effective in predicting effluent parameters, but studies show that models like SVR and ANN can outperform it in certain cases. Feed-forward neural networks and DL methods, such as DenseNet, also demonstrate high accuracy in predicting effluent quality parameters.
- Various AI models, including CNNs and hybrid neural network–GAs, have shown promise in monitoring and predicting key parameters like FOG accumulation in pumping stations, SVI, and activated sludge bulking. This contributes to better management of high-flow situations and enhances efficiency in the face of hydraulic loading difficulties.
- Studies have indicated that advanced algorithms, such as FL, NNs, and boosting methods, can improve flow management while achieving significant energy savings in pumping stations and aeration control within treatment processes.

Further AI research is recommended to focus on the development of hybrid modeling approaches that integrate data-driven and knowledge-driven models. Additionally, incorporating those operational models with hydrological forecasting for the prediction of flow rates, resulting from rainfall in advance, could significantly enhance the management of increased flow rates and mitigate sewer overflows. It is also recommended to explore the potential applications of AI to address other consequences of climate change, such as temperature rise, sea-level rise, and saltwater intrusion into WWTPs.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

All relevant data are included in the paper or its Supplementary Information.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare there is no conflict.

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